

AYURVEDIC VIEW ON VARDHAKYAJANITA, INDRIYAPRADOSHOJA VIKARA AND THEIR MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Jara is referred to in *Sushruta Samhita* as a *Swabhavabala Pravritta Vyadhi*; it is a condition of nature that occurs progressively with the decay of *Dhatu*. Depending on whether *Vata Dosha* is dominant or not, it creates variation in *Sharira* and *Manas* function. In modern times, there has been an increase in the prevalence of geriatric sensory and mental disorders, which include depression, anxiety, insomnia and anxiety, etc. All of these can be described as *Vardhakyajanita Vikara* and/or *Indriya Pradoshaja Vikara*. Their respective cause include *Asatmendriyartha Samyoga*, *Prajnaparadha* and *Parinama*; leading to *Dosha* vitiation and *Srotodushti*. The treatment approach typically used for managing these conditions include use of *Rasayana*, use of *Panchakarma (Basti and Nasya)*, use of *Sattvavajaya Chikitsa* and lifestyle modifications. Treatment focuses on both *Dravyabhuta* as well as *Adravyabhuta* interventions to promote healthy aging and to preserve sensory and mental health.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda, Vardhakyajanita Vikara, Jara, Rasayana, Sattvavajaya Chikitsa.***INTRODUCTION**

According to Ayurveda the effect of aging on the body and mind due to the gradual decrease in the *Dhatu* and *Jnanendriya*. Ayurvedic medicine employs *Jara Tantra* which is one of the *Ashtanga* specialties of Ayurveda that is devoted to the study of nutrition, immunology, and the treatment of geriatrics. Aging is a natural process that is experienced by everyone and always leads to death. Anxiety, depression and insomnia are common mental illness found in elderly population. *Tridoshas* are the root causes of all functions in the body. When the *Svabhava* and *Karma* of the *Dosha*, as well as their *Ojas*, are complete, then the corresponding *Dhatu* and *Srotas* can no longer perform their functions, leading to *Srotodusti*. This condition associated with *Atipravrutti*, *Vimargagati*, *Siragranthi* and *Sanga*, etc.^[1,4]

Similarly diseases related to the *Indriya* can be explained as *Indriya Pradoshaja Vikaras*. Elderly individuals often experience *Indriya Pradoshaja Vikara* symptoms associated with the five sense organs; the most common include *Timira* and other sensory loss. It is imperative to understand the *Nidana* and *Samprapti* of the diseases in order to develop an effective treatment plan because the major treatment options for *Indriya Pradoshaja Vikaras* includes *Nidana parivarjana* and *Samprapti vighatana*. The avoidance of causative factors and dissociation of natural pathogenesis of disease play vital role in the management of *Indriya Pradoshaja Vikaras*. This article explains Ayurvedic view and management of *Vardhakyajanita* and *Indriyapradoshaja Vikara*. The general principles of managing these disorders are depicted in **Figure 1**.^[4,6]

Figure 1: General therapeutic principles of Ayurveda.

Vardhakyajanita Vikara and their Management

The increase of *Vata Dosha* in old age is a major factor for the *Vardhakyajanita Vikara* symptoms. The most common *Vardhakyajanita Vikara* symptoms manifested by *Vata* excess include degenerative diseases: *Sandhigata Vata*, *Gridhrasi*, *Pakshaghata* and arthritis, etc. Neuro-psychiatric symptoms include memory and cognitive degeneration such as depression, *Nidranasha*, Alzheimer's disease and anxiety, etc. Additional examples of common complaints include weakness, malnutrition, *Vyadhikshamatwa Heenata*, urinary problems and anemia, etc.

Management of *Vardhakyajanita Vikara* focuses on a comprehensive approach promoting maximizing health through improved nutritional supply, maintaining balance between the three *Doshas* and prolonging life through *Rasayana* therapies. These improve the quality of the *Dhatus* and promoting maximum health. *Amalaki*, *Ashwagandha*, *Brahmi* and *Guduchi*, etc. are *Rasayana* medicines that support immunity, vitality and cognitive function. In addition to the use of *Rasayana* herbs and therapies for the treatment of *Vardhakyajanita Vikara*, the use of *Panchakarma* therapies is required for detoxification purpose.^[5,7]

- ✓ *Abhyanga* and *Svedana* therapies are critical to reducing the aggravation of *Vata Dosha* and improving joint mobility.
- ✓ *Basti* is considered to be the most effective treatment for all *Vata*-related disorders, but especially for degenerative diseases.
- ✓ *Kati Basti* is often used as a treatment for lower back pain.
- ✓ *Nasya* can improve the function of the senses and cognition.

It is recommended that elderly person should consume nourishing and wholesome foods that are easy to digest and following the principles of *Pathya-Apathya*. *Shamana Chikitsa* includes using *Rasa Aushadhis* and *Medhya Rasayana* for improving cognition and memory among the elderly. Mental health is addressed through

Sattvavajaya Chikitsa which assists to build a healthy mind and help to manage feelings of anxiety, fear and depression. Other treatment options will include those that are disease-specific. The primary goal of treating *Vardhakyajanita Vikara* is to maintain *Swasthya* and to provide an optimal quality of life by preventing and delaying degenerative changes and supporting good aging.^[6,8]

Indriya Pradoshaja Vikara and their Management

The *Indriya Stithsa dosha* can be *Dushita* by using *Nidana sevana* and result in *Indriya Pradoshaja Vikara*. In Ayurveda *Indriya Pradoshaja Vikara* are defined as the product of the influence of *Pradosha* or imbalance of *Vata* and *Pitta* on either one or more of the five *Jnanendriyas*. The *Jnanendriyas* are *Chakshu*, *Shrotra*, *Ghrana*, *Rasana* and *Tvak* which are all controlled by specific *Dosha*. The vitiation may occur when there is an imbalance due to *Asatmya Ahara*, *Mithya Vihara*, and suppression of natural urges and excessive uses of *Indriyas*.

The approach to the management of *Indriya Pradoshaja Vikara* by Ayurveda is based on the balancing of vitiation of *Doshas*. The use of *Raktamokshana* and *Nitya Sevaniya-Aahar* may help to restore healthy function of the sense organs. The use of *Shirodhara*, *Nasya* and other lifestyle changes helps to treat both *Upatapa* and *Upaghata*. Treatment approaches for the *Netra Roga* include *Putpaka*, *Tarpana*, *Seka* and *Aschyotana*, these all used to address various forms of *Timira*. For the auditory system (*Karna*), procedures such as *Karna Poorana* can be used to treat *Badhirya*. Ayurveda suggested many types of *Nasya* to treat *Ghranendriya* (olfactory) dysfunctions. *Shodhana* techniques such as *Nasya*, *Raktamokshana* and *Shirovirechana* help to cleanse the individual of deeply seated toxins.^[7,9] It is recommended that one should follow *Sadvritta* and *Prajnaparadha* concepts to avoid disease causative factors. The common *Indriya Pradoshaja Vikara* and their specific management are presented in **Table 1**.^[6,9]

Table 1: Indriya Pradoshaja Vikara and their Specific Management.

Indriya	Common Conditions	Management
Chakshurindriya	Timira, Abhishyanda and Linganasha	Chakshushya Ahara, Netra Tarpana, Putapaka, Aschyotana, Triphala Rasayana, etc.
Shrotrendriya	Karnashoola, Badhirya and Karnanada	Karna Purana, Nasya Karma and Anuvasana Basti, etc.
Ghranendriya	Pratishyaya, Peenasa, Anosmia	Nasya Karma, Dhumapana and Vamana
Rasanendriya	Aruchi, Mukha Paka and Glossitis	Kavala & Gandusha, Deepana-Pachana (Trikatu and Chitraka)
Tvagindriya	Kustha, Visarpa, Itching and Dermatitis	Raktamokshana, Shamana (Neem and Khadira) Lepa and Abhyanga.

CONCLUSION

The elderly population suffers from health problems due to *Dhatu Kshaya*, a predominance of *Vata* and chronic exposure to causative factors such as *Prajnaparadha* and *Asatmendriyarth Samyoga*. Therapeutic modalities such as *Rasayana* therapy, *Panchakarma* therapies, including *Nasya* and *Basti*, *Shamana Chikitsa* and *Sattvavajaya Chikitsa* contribute to restoring the balance of *Dosha* and the normal function of the sense organs in elderly. Further support of the concepts of *Pathya-Apathya*, *Achara Rasayana* and a disciplined lifestyle all contribute to enhancing *Vyadhikshamatva* through slower degenerative changes. Ayurveda provides relief by using pharmacological, non-pharmacological and life-style modification to promote healthy aging through longevity with functional independence and mental well-being.

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